

Environmental Variables and Career Choice of Secondary School Students in Osun State Nigeria

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Abstract

the study investigated the environmental variables and the career choice of secondary school students in Osun State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent to which the environmental variables influence the career choice of secondary school students in Osun State. A question was raised to guide the study, and one hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study employed a descriptive research survey design. 1,500 students were sampled from all the secondary school in Osun State. The multistage sampling method was used to select the sample for the study. A self-designed instrument named (EVCCQ) was used to collect relevant information for the study. Validation of the instrument was done through face, content and test-re-test method. Data collected were analyzed using frequency count, percentage and ANOVA were done to answer the only hypothesis formulated. The results revealed that family background, valued societal job, peer group, school environment and religious background of the subjects influence their career choice in Osun-State. It was recommended that parents are always enjoined to encourage their words. They, however, advised not to force their will on the children. School counseling unit of school should put in place programme that will help the students to discover their potential, ability, and capability at fixing into a particular career.

Key Word: Career, Family Background, Societal Valued Job, Peer Group, School Environment, Religious Background, Career Choice

Introduction

Secondary school Education in Nigeria serves as a link between the primary school Education and higher school Education and this play a very important role in the choice of a career. A child's future career seems to depend on the type of education he/she received at the secondary school level. Apart from establishing the roots of education of a child, secondary school education appears to be instrumental in shaping and directing the child to a bright future career. This stage of education serves as a mean to move on to a higher stage as well as to provide generic competencies that cut across the various domain of knowledge and skills (Ekundayo, 2010)

The desire to use education for a nation building is still very compelling. So predominant was the faith that the schools of a nation were not only meant for political socialization but also for other social functions and for economic growth. This is especially informed by the rapid change of the predominant traditional agricultural practice of the past to an industrial one today. Furthermore, the drift of people from rural to urban area seems to have affected the family occupations of the past and the present day career choice of Nigerian adolescents. Since survey studies of (Ige, 2015 and Babatunde, 2010) have shown that a large number of young adults in Nigeria leave school or even complete their last years in secondary school and sometimes their first year of higher education without giving any thought to their future career and without acquiring skills that could be used directly in productive work, a vital need exists to turn to the schools to help children and youths understand the meaning of work in the life of a person and to prepare them for their career as worker.

The problem of career choice seems to have implications for national development. In every society, the quality of workers, as well as the degree of job satisfaction, contributes directly or indirectly to economic stability and the smooth running of the affairs of a nation. If workers are unable to derive satisfaction from their job, frustration sets in with an accompanying decline in the productivity and civil unrest due to the workers thwarted goals (Soethout, Ten and van, 2004). Career was described as a way of life. It moulds one's character, determines one's social status, income, style of life, choice of friends and mental and physical health (Udoh and Sanni, 2012). This implies that the choice of career has a persuasive connection with one's entire way of life.

Many are the variables that operate to decide which career an individual chooses. Practically, every effort put forth to decide a career translates to an effort that limits oneself from entering into a wide array of careers. A number of variables seem to impact more strongly than others. However, while it is difficult to determine the relative potency of these variables. It is, therefore, true that there are some forms of interaction among the variables where one modifies the other. While some of these variables are psychological and biologically rooted, others have socio-economic undertones. Still, it is not uncommon for an individual to get into a career by accident or chance (Udoh and Sanni, 2012)

Salami and Salami (2013) discovered that before a student chooses a career; so many factors must have been taken into consideration. Therefore, it is evident that no student chooses a career without being influenced by one factor or the other such as family or parental influence of background, societal valued jobs, and religious background and so on. Research studies of (Shumba and Naong, 2012 and Faleye and Adams, 2008) have shown that families, parents and guidance in particular play a significant role in the occupational aspirations and career development of their children. Significant people in the family like father, mother and siblings are a great source of aspiration for some children, especially when they are counted with the type of career they have adopted. Peer group also appear to play a prominent role in the career choice of secondary school students. Black (2002) said peer group provides a forum when teenagers constrict and reconstruct their identities. A peer-labeling process may contribute to the construction of positive identities for some adolescents but negative identities for others, especially in the chosen of career.

A student's educational outcome and academic success are greatly influenced by the type of school he/she attend. School factors include school structure school location, composition, and climate (Barry, 2006). The school one attends the institutional environment that set the parameter of a student learning experience Nigerians, and most especially the people of Osun State are highly religious people. The state is a confluence of three religions, Christian, Islam, and Traditional. Within these religions, there are a number of divisions or denominations and each striving for recognition on the youth's career choices. Thomas and James, (2001) speak on the role of religion in career choice has suggested that religion relate positively to desirable career development outcome such as occupational decisions. Based upon this background, this paper, therefore, investigates the extent to which family Background, peer group, valued social job, school environment and religious background of secondary school students in the Osun State of Nigeria influence their career choice A question was raised to guide the study:

- (1) What extent would the environmental variables influence the career choice of secondary school students in Osun State, Nigeria? Based on the research question raised to guide the study, one null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There will be no significant sex difference in the influence of environmental variables on the career choice of secondary school students in Osun State.

Methodology

The study employed the use of descriptive research on survey type. The population for the study consisted of all the secondary school students in Osun State. There were 329 secondary schools with a population of 125, 020 students in the public secondary school in the State at the time of this study. (Osun State Ministry of Education, 2018). 1,500 students were drawn from the entire population. The multistage sampling procedure was used in the sample selection. Two local government areas were selected from selected of the three senatorial districts that made up the state. Two public secondary schools were also selected from each of the local government areas using stratified and simple random sampling method. The schools were stratified into rural and urban schools, where all the schools in the local government headquarters were regarded as urban schools and other schools outside the local government headquarters were regarded as rural schools. 125 students were drawn from each school at the third stage using stratified and simple random sampling techniques.

Research Instrument

A self-constructed questionnaire titled "Environmental variables and career choice Questionnaire" (EVCCQ) was used to collect information from students. The questionnaire is of two sections. Section A sought information on demographic variables, while section B help to elicit information on environmental variables on career choice.

Validation of Instrument

The validity of the instrument was ensured through the face and content validity, while the reliability was ascertained through test-re-test method. Copies of the instrument were administered twice within two weeks interval on a set of twenty-five students that are not part of the subjects sampled for the study. The scores generated from the two administrations were corrected. Pearson product moment correlation coefficient of 0.78 was got, and this was high enough to determine the reliability of the instrument

Administration of Instrument and data Analysis

Copies of the questionnaire were administered on the respondents by the researchers with the help of research assistants in each school. The completed copies were collected by the researchers immediately before moving to

another school. descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. Frequency count, percentage and mean scores were used to answer the only general question raised, while ANOVA was used to test the only hypothesis formulated at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

To determine the extent to which environmental variables influence the choice of secondary school students' career. The data collected were analyzed and described using frequency count, percentages, mean scores, and Ranking.

Table 1: Frequency count and percentage on the influence of environmental variables on career choice

Variable	AGREE		DISAGREE		MEAN	RANK
	F	%	F	%		
Family Background	9021	60.1	5979	39.9	1.60	1 st
Peer Group	8169	54.5	6831	45.5	1.54	3 rd
Societal Value Job	9021	60.1	5979	39.9	1.60	1 st
School Environment	7686	51.2	7314	48.8	1.51	4 th
Religious Background	5679	37.9	9321	62.1	1.38	5 th

Table 1 revealed the extent to which the variables influence the career choice of the subjects. Family Background and societal valued job variables with 60.1% and 60.1% respectively be the highest variables that influence the career choice of these youths. Peer group influence was rank next to family background and valued societal job with 54.5% of the total respondents with the mean score of 1.54 School environment rank 4th with 51.2% of the respondent, and mean score of 1.51. Religious background is the least with 37.9% of the respondents that were in agreement that religion influence the choice of the career with a mean score of 1.38.

To test the formulated hypothesis, Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used

Table 2

ANOVA is showing the influence of environmental variables on secondary school students. Career choice

Source	Ss	Df	Ms	F	P
Corrected Model	117963.598	25	4718.544	16.415	.000
A	172.085	1	172.085	.599	.439
B	5661.651	1	5661.651	19.694	.000
C	1188.560	1	1188.560	4.134	.042
D	1309.198	1	1309.198	4.554	.041
E	1888.763	1	1888.761	6.570	.029
F	1238.290	1	1238.290	4.307	.38
A*B*C*D*E*F	1139.008	1	1139.008	3.962	.049
Error	423749.385	1474	287.483		
Total	1921000.000	1500			
Correlated Total	541712.983	1499			

A: sex, B. Family Background, C. Peer Groups, D. Societal valued job, E. School Environment, F. Religion

Table 2 reveals that there is a significant sex difference in the influence of environmental variables on the career choice of the students. ($F_{1,1474}=3.962$, $P<0.05$). The null hypothesis is rejected. The main effect of family Background ($F_{1,1474}=19.694$, $P<0.05$). Peer group ($F_{1,1474}=4.134$, $P<0.05$), Societal valued job ($F_{1,1474}=4.554$, $P<0.05$), School Environment ($F_{1,1474}=6.570$, $P<0.05$), and Religion ($F_{1,1474}=3.962$, $P<0.05$) on career choice of secondary school students in the state under study. However, the effect of gender of career choice of secondary school students is significant at 0.05 level ($F_{1,1474}=0.599$, $P>0.05$)

Discussion

The study showed that family background, peer group, valued societal job, school environment, and religion influencing career choice of secondary school students in the state under this study. The family dynamic and interaction such as attachment, this environment plays a dominant role in the children's career choice. This finding is in line with the findings of Madu (2011) that, there is a positive relationship between children's early rearing experience and their occupational choice. The study also revealed a significant school environmental influence on the students' career choice. The finding is in agreement with the work of Akintomide and Oluwatosin (2011) that presentation of materials, interactions with students, class atmosphere and students attitude to learning have significant influences on the education acquire toward career choice. The study shows

that activities of some role models in the society influence their career choice while the majority of secondary school students in the study area believed that catalog of some professional achievements in their vicinity influences their career choice. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Abouche did (2007) and Ekundayo (2010) that societal demands are caused by a change in a social context on career and their relevance to the immediate political, economic, social and career trends. The results also showed that there was a significant religion influence on career choice of secondary school students in the study area. The result tends credence to the works of Moore (2011), and Mattis and Jagers (2001) that parents saw low encouraging a religious identity affects their children's behavior patterns at home and outside their preview and then concluded that religion is a strong force in determining the career choice of youths in any society.

Conclusion and Recommendations

By the revelation of the study, it was concluded that environmental variables such as family background, valued societal job, peer group, school environment, and religious background were important variables that influence the career choice of secondary school students in Osun State Nigeria. On the basis of the findings, it is recommended that parents are enjoyed to always encourage their words accordingly in order to select an appropriate career. They are however advised not to force their will on the children so as to avoid any consequential effect of their acts. The school counselor should always organize career talk inviting some professionals to talking on their career. Counselling unit of the school should put in place programmes that will help the students to discover their potentiality, ability, and capability at fixing into a particular career.

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